

Disease progress curves based on HRLH (%), DS (%), DI (%), SES, and real area infected for vertical development of ShB on 3 rice cultivars in the screenhouse. Each point is the mean of four replications. Vertical lines indicate standard errors.

quantitative data, actual measurement of injury is necessary.

Some difficulties were encountered in using RAI. Because infected leaves and sheaths have to be detached from the plant, the plant may be damaged before

maturity. The method is also tedious. At later growth stages, infected leaves and sheaths of lower plant parts cause difficulties in determining RAI. This method needs to be modified and tested for improved efficiency.

HRLH and DS are the most convenient and dependable assessment methods: they are easy to use and discriminate among cultivars. ■

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) on swamp rice in Guinea

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Symptoms of presumed RYMV were observed on cultivated rice in mangrove and inland swamps of Coyah and Koba Districts, lower Guinea, 1982-1986. The chrysomelid beetle vectors of RYMV, *Chaetocnema* sp., were also observed at the same sites.

In 1986, some naturally infected rice plants were collected from a mangrove swamp at Yelimangeya, Coya District, and maintained in buckets on a 180-d duration, virus-susceptible rice cultivar CP4 at Rokupr, Sierra Leone. Similar naturally virus-infected rice plants were collected at Rokupr and Makoth in Kambia District and at Kabala in Koinadugu District in the Northern Province of Sierra Leone in 1988 and 1989 cropping seasons. These isolates

were maintained on CP4 by the same method.

In 1989, agar-gel double diffusion tests were done with crude extracts from virus-infected rice plants that had typical pale yellow mottling symptoms. Viruliferous saps were extracted in 0.01 M phosphate buffer solution, pH 7. (Antiserum was obtained from IITA.)

Reactions of virus antigens and anti-serum were strongly positive. No spur formation was observed between the virus isolates of Guinea and Sierra Leone and the antiserum from Nigeria. This indicates serological similarity between RYMV isolates and probably their common identity. ■

Hosts of rice tungro-associated viruses (RTVs) in Thailand

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We used enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and latex agglutination test to detect rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) and rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in 10 weed species, 12

species of wild rice, 27 lines of wild rice, wheat, barley, and maize.

The plants were inoculated separately with viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* that had fed on RTVs-infected rice plants for 4 d. Each species had uninoculated plants as control. The vectors were confined on test plants at 5 insects/seedling for 24 h of inoculation. Inoculated seedlings were kept in the greenhouse.

The second youngest leaf of each plant was collected 30 days after inoculation and homogenized with phosphate buffer saline. Extracts of